

Physico-chemical Analysis of the MEHDIA Estuary (GHARB –MOROCCO)

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Abstract—In Morocco, superficial flows are dependent on rainfall and exhibit high spatial variability. In general, the water resources available to Morocco are limited and subject to extreme cyclical variations. Similarly, the qualitative situation of the waters is far from satisfactory. Indeed, population growth accompanied by rapid urbanization that causes many disturbances to natural environments. Industrialization, the irrational use of fertilizers and pesticides and the lack of awareness of the population towards the protection of the environment, lead as much to an imbalance of the ecosystem and generate polluting elements that can affect the physico-chemical quality biological and aquatic environments, but also alter the uses of water; water collection, swimming ... etc. The sub-basin of OuedSebou drains the Mehdiya region and is particularly affected by the problem of continuous development of the agricultural sector. Indeed, the discharges of water-gardens, pesticides and fertilizers drained by rainwater and irrigation and dirt environment, in addition to the domestic discharges generated by the small town Mehdiya and the city of Kenitra are dumped directly into the OuedSebou. The present research on the Mehdiya region is aimed at the prospection of the hydrobiology of the waters of the Sebouwadi. The study will be based on physicochemical analysis of the mouth of Mehdiya and the determination of seasonal fluctuations of these parameters between the low water period and the flood period.

Keywords—Morocco, sebou river, hydrochemistry, Mehdiya, gharb.

I. INTRODUCTION

In Morocco, superficial flows are dependent on rainfall and exhibit high spatial variability [1-2]. In general, the water resources available to Morocco are limited and subject to extreme cyclical variations [3]. Similarly, the qualitative situation of the waters is far from satisfactory [4]. Indeed, population growth accompanied by rapid urbanization that causes many disturbances to natural environments [5]. Industrialization, the irrational use of fertilizers and pesticides and the lack of awareness of the population towards the protection of the environment, lead as much to an imbalance of the ecosystem and generate polluting elements that can affect the physico-chemical quality biological and aquatic environments [6], but also alter the uses of water; water collection, swimming ... etc [7]. The sub-basin of OuedSebou drains the Mehdiya region and is particularly affected by the problem of continuous development of the agricultural sector [8]. Indeed, the discharges of water-gardens, pesticides and fertilizers drained by rainwater and irrigation and dirt environment, in addition to the domestic discharges generated by the small town Mehdiya and the city of Kenitra are dumped directly into the OuedSebou [9]. The present research on the Mehdiya region is aimed at the prospection of the hydrobiology of the waters of the Sebouwadi. The study will be based on physicochemical analysis of the mouth of Mehdiya and the determination of seasonal fluctuations of these parameters between the low water period and the flood period.

II. STUDY SITE

This is a city in Morocco. It is located in the region of Rabat-Salé-Kenitra. It is a picturesque coastal town located near the town of Kenitra 30 km north-east of the capital Rabat. The fishing port, very picturesque at the mouth of the OuedSebou, the proximity of the SidiBoughaba Lake Biological Reserve with its forests and rare bird colonies, the Spanish, Portuguese and Dutch forts, the Kasbah of Yaqub al-Mansur, and the proximity of the ancient sites of Banasa and Thamusida are undeniable assets to develop tourism of this village, still little known. Its long sandy beaches are also very popular with surfers and bodyboarders. Mehdiya has a population of 16,262.

Coordinates: 34° 15' 21" north, 6° 40' 28" West

Altitude: 31 m

FIG 1: The Coordinates of Mehdiya

FIG 2: Geographical Limits of the Province of Kenitra

FIG 3: Geographical Localization of the study area (Mâamora Tablecloth) in Yel

III. STUDY METHOD

Four stations S1 to S24, distributed along the Sebouwadi, have been retained in such a way that they are accessible and reflect the real characteristics of the surface water of the Sebouwadi at the level of the Mehdiya study area.

IV. SAMPLING AND ANALYSIS

Along the Oued Sebou and throughout the study area, water samples were taken in 16 points. At each sampling, the samples were kept in plastic bottles, previously rinsed with water from the station. The bottles were then transported to the laboratory at 4° C. The temperature is measured "in-situ" using a mercury thermometer graduated 1/10 from 0 to 50 ° C. The hydrogen potential (pH), the EC electrical conductivity, the dissolved oxygen (O₂) is determined using a CONSORT-Model 835 multi-parameter analyzer, an oximeter and a pH meter. The suspended solids MES are determined by filtration of a volume of water on 0.45 µm cellulose filter according to Rodier [10]. BOD₅ is determined by the respiratory method using a WTW DBO-meter model 1020T according to the technique described by DIN [11]. The COD is determined by acid oxidation by the excess of potassium dichromate at the temperature of 148° C of the oxidizable materials under the conditions of the test in the presence of silver sulfate as catalyst and mercury sulphate according to DIN [12]. The chlorides are determined by a volumetric acid determination (HNO₃) by a solution of mercuric nitrate in the presence of a pH indicator. Nitrates, ammonium and orthophosphates are analyzed by colorimetric methods using a Visible Type 722 S Beijing UV spectrophotometer.

FIG 4: Method of assays and titrations of mineral elements in the water of the lower sebou

V. RESULT AND DISCUSSIONS

The assessment of raw water pollution of the Lower Sebou was made according to the determination of a certain number of physicochemical parameters characterizing the waters. In the light of this work which contributes to enriching the bases of the data accumulated on the basin of Sebou, and to make it possible to clarify the degree of its pollution thanks to the results obtained during the period of our internship within the Regional Office of Implementation. Agricultural value of GharbKenitra. It can be deduced that the Lower Sebou sub-basin is subject to different types of pollution of natural origin that are mainly mineral (by natural substrate dissolution, Atlantic tides) and anthropogenic (agricultural, industrial and urban). The thermal regime of the Sebou hydrographic network follows that of the Mediterranean climate, cold in November and warmer in summer. The pH does not show any significant variations and the waters are generally alkaline ranging between 8.01 and 8.78 following their travels of limestone and marl-limestone soils characterizing the basin. The mineralization follows suitably the rates of dissolved salts, salinity, chlorides, sodium and potassium. It results mainly from the leaching of the karst limestone-traversed terrain and oceanic spray. Indeed, the electrical conductivity that reflects salinity (Fig 5) varies from 4000 to 25000 $\mu\text{s} / \text{cm}$ and far exceeds the Moroccan irrigation standard ($> 2700 \mu\text{s} / \text{cm}$) [12-14]. Concerning the nitrate contents (Fig. 6), the values vary between 0.24 mg / L and 2692 mg / L and clearly reflect the pollution of agricultural origin by the nitrogen fertilizers, the wastewater and leachates of the wild discharges [15-21].

FIG 5: Spatial evolution of the pH of the raw water of the lower sebou-mehdia

FIG 6: Spatial evolution of [Cl-]

FIG 7: Spatial evolution of the electrical conductivity of the raw waters of the sous-sebou-mehdia

FIG 8: Spatial evolution of [Na+]

FIG 9: Projection in the piper diagram of hydrochemistry waters of the lower basin of sebou

FIG 10: Piper Diagram of low Sebou river

FIGURE 11: Diagram of the raw water quality classes of the sub basin of the lower Sebou and projection of the raw water quality of the subbasin of the lower Sebou in the Wilcox diagram

VI. CONCLUSION

Adjacent agricultural activities occur in the waters of the Lower Sebou sub-basin by significant concentrations of nitrates and sulphates that enter the water stream by runoff and leaching of nitrogenous and phosphorus fertilizer and phytosanitary products [26-27]. The upstream-downstream distribution of physicochemical parameters reflects degraded situations of water quality in salts and chlorides in relationships.

The present work has revealed the poor quality of the waters of the lower Sebou but remains incomplete and needs to be deepened by analyzes of trace heavy metals and pesticides to provide the scientific and technical bases for decision makers [28-30].

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